

REINFORCEMENTS DISTRIBUTION AND RELATED MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES BY INVESTMENT CASTING

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1. Introduction

Titanium matrix composites (TMCs) have several attractive characteristics, such as elastic modulus, high temperature property, wear and oxidation resistance. However, it is adopted in limited area, such as aerospace and automobile, because of its high manufacturing cost and extreme affinity in molten state [1]. Generally, in the case of metal matrix composites, it is desirable to select the reinforcements which exhibit the suitable interface with the matrix, high temperature stability and similar coefficient of thermal expansion compared with the matrix [2]. Among reinforcements, TiB and TiC have an outstanding compatibility with the Ti matrix, because of the similar density, analogous coefficient of thermal expansion [3]. Despite extensive work on the manufacturing of the particulate reinforced TMCs, previous researches were mostly based on the powder metallurgy, since the process temperature was relatively lower than the casting process, and it is easy to control the exact composition [4]. However, processing steps were very complicated and an agglomeration of reinforcements which occur the deterioration of mechanical property. Expensive fine powder can also be an obstacle to apply industrial fields. In case of casting process, it can provide the economical and soundness of final casting. *In-situ* synthesis, such as SHS and XDTM technique, which known as using the reaction between matrix and adding element, also assures the homogeneous distribution of reinforcement and clean interface between the matrix and reinforcement [5-7]. In this research, we adopt to the investment casting process for the economical considerations. In addition, *in-situ* synthesis method also developed to ensure not only homogeneous distribution but also controlled interfacial reaction between the matrix and

reinforcements. Boron carbide was added to the Ti matrix using vacuum induction melting which can provide the *in-situ* reaction of $5\text{Ti} + \text{B}_4\text{C} = 4\text{TiB} + \text{TiC}$. The *in-situ* synthesized (TiB+TiC) reinforcements in the Ti matrix were examined and the tensile and tribological properties of TMCs were also investigated with respect to the B₄C size and content.

2. Experimental Procedure

The mold for TMCs was prepared by the investment casting process, so called lost-wax method. Prepared mold was mounted in the vacuum induction melting furnace. After that, different sizes (1500 and 150 μm) and contents (0.94, 1.88 and 3.76wt%) B₄C (99 % purity) was added to pure Ti (99% purity, Grade 2) in order to form the 5, 10 and 20vol% (TiB+TiC) reinforcement. The melts were poured into the mold by a 10G centrifugal force. The tensile tests of the TMCs were conducted in a MTS 810 universal testing machine. Each tensile specimen was machined according to the ASTM E8 subsize which was given a gage length of 25mm and gage width with 6mm. Specimens were machined with grip regions that were 17mm wide by 35mm long at each end of the sample. The TMCs specimens of this investigation were subjected to mechanical testing with variable B₄C sizes and contents under the initial strain rate of 0.001/s at room temperature. The ball-on-disk type friction tester was used to obtain the performance data of friction and wear of the TMCs. The disk was formed cylindrically by 30mm of diameter and the diameter of the friction test track was 20mm. The ball specimen was used by 52100 bearing steel, which was fixed to the load cell to measure the friction force. The applied load was about 3.5N and the sliding speed was 120 rpm

(125mm/s). Friction test was carried out for 30 minutes under not lubricated conditions.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Effect of B₄C Size on Microstructure of TMCs

From Fig. 1, as increasing B₄C content, the size of reinforcements was increased. There is a dramatic change in the reinforcement, especially in needle like TiB. The *in-situ* synthesized reinforcements prepared with 150 μ m B₄C were very fine and were distributed more homogeneously than 1500 μ m B₄C.

Fig. 1. Microstructure of (a) pure Ti and *in-situ* synthesized TMCs with B₄C: 1,500 μ m (b) 0.94wt%, (c) 1.88wt%, (d) 3.76wt%, and B₄C: 150 μ m (e) 0.94wt%, (f) 1.88wt%, (g) 3.76wt%

Fig. 2 shows the bright image and spot diffraction pattern of synthesized TiB and TiC reinforcements.

Based on the results of the diffraction pattern analysis, Fig. 2(a) and (b) indicate that the TiB reinforcement has an orthorhombic structure originating from the [002] zone axis. The needle shaped phase which was thought to be TiB was analyzed by TEM. In addition, Fig. 2(c) and (d) corresponds to the TiC reinforcement that has a cubic (NaCl) structure originating from the [002] zone axis. Thus, it was confirmed that needle-like TiB and spherical TiC were formed by the *in-situ* synthesis of Ti and B₄C by the melting route.

Fig. 2. The results of TEM analysis of Ti-1.88wt%B₄C (B₄C: 150 μ m) composites, (a) bright field image of (a) Ti and TiB, (c) Ti and TiC, spot diffraction pattern of synthesized (b) TiB and (d) TiC.

Furthermore, the size and morphology of *in-situ* reinforcements were quite different according to the B₄C size of 1500 and 150 μ m. In the case of the conventional manufacturing process of MMCs, the size and morphology of reinforcements was maintained except for the interfacial reaction between the matrix and reinforcement since the reinforcements were added directly to the matrix.

However, the reinforcements were synthesized by the chemical reaction between the matrix and specific additive. For this reason, the size, morphology and distribution of the reinforcements

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by *in-situ* reaction were considerably influenced by the process parameter such as the reaction time, superheating and cooling rate. Notably, despite maintaining the same above-mentioned process parameter, the size, morphology and distribution of the *in-situ* reinforcements (especially TiB) due to 150 μ m B₄C shows a clear distinction compared with the 1500 μ m B₄C. From these results, it is believed that fine B₄C particles promote the increase of the number of the nucleation sites for the reinforcements due to the *in-situ* reaction. Furthermore, the microstructures of TMCs reveal that there are no particular reaction layer between the matrix and reinforcement.

2.2 Mechanical Properties of TMCs

2.2.1 Tensile Property of Particulate Reinforced TMCs

Fig. 3 and 4 indicate the tensile property of TMCs with respect to the B₄C sizes and contents. It is obvious that as the reinforcement content increased, tensile strength was increased and ductility was decreased comparing with unreinforced pure Ti. In addition, the TMCs produced by fine B₄C improved the tensile elongation and the strength was improved by a small margin. Notably, the tensile elongation of the TMCs due to 150 μ m B₄C were about from 1.5 to 2.0 times higher than that resulting from the 1500 μ m B₄C.

Fig. 3. Yield strength of *in-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites at room temperature. (YS: yield strength)

Fig. 4. Tensile elongation of *in-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites at room temperature.

In the viewpoint of the tensile strength improvement, the conventional strengthening mechanisms of MMCs were divided mainly into three parts, such as shear-lag strengthening, dislocation density strengthening and Orowan strengthening [1]. In this research, we focused on the shear-lag strengthening which was based on the load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcements by means of interfacial shear stress. According to Cox and Nardone [9,10], the tensile strength was improved by the load transfer phenomena.

Fig. 5. Inverse pole figure maps of (a) pure Ti, and Ti-1.88wt%B₄C composites with (b) 1500μm B₄C, (c) 150μm B₄C.

Fig. 6. Mean diameter of reinforcements of *in-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites.

To predict the tensile strength by load transfer strengthening, the mean size and aspect ratio of the reinforcements of TMCs by the 1500 and 150μm B₄C were measured using IMAGE PRO PLUS software. Fig. 3 indicates the results of the calculated and experimental tensile strength of the TMCs by 1500 and 150μm. Comparing the calculated tensile strength of the TMCs as a results of different B₄C size, there are few differences between the 1500 and 150μm B₄C. Besides, the experimental tensile strength was much higher than the calculated value by the load transfer mechanism. It is hard to explain the effect of the reinforcement size on the tensile strength and elongation. Therefore, we focused on the grain reduction effect on the tensile property as well as the load transfer strengthening. From the well-known Hall-Petch relation, the yield stress is inversely proportional to the grain size, and this was based on the concept that the grain boundary acts as a barrier to dislocation motion [11]. EBSD analysis was adopted to measure the matrix grain size. This method can obtain exact information of the specific phase based on the crystal orientation by the diffraction pattern. The grain size of the alpha-Ti of the TMCs was much lower value comparing those of pure Ti as shown Fig. 5 and 6. Furthermore, all the contents, the average grain size of TMCs from the fine B₄C was lower compared to the coarse B₄C. Therefore,

we conclude that the improvement of the tensile property was obtained owing to the matrix grain refinement and homogeneous distribution as well as owing to load transfer strengthening.

2.2.2 Wear Property of Particulate Reinforced TMCs

Fig. 7 shows the worn surface of pure Ti and TMCs by SEM. Among several wear mechanism, abrasive wear is dominant mechanism in this case.

Fig. 7. Wear track of (a) pure Ti, and *in-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites with, B₄C: 1500μm (b) 0.94wt%, (c) 1.88wt%, (d) 3.76wt%, and B₄C: 150μm (e) 0.94wt%, (f) 1.88wt%, (g) 3.76wt%.

In common, lots of scratches are founded on the worn surface in pure Ti and Ti-0.94wt%B₄C. In case of pure Ti and Ti-0.94wt%B₄C, as shown in Fig.

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7(a), (b) and (e), the surface is worn by abrasion and plastic deformation. In addition, many cracks are observed on the worn surface. Because of these cracks propagation, the size of wear debris is getting larger. In the results of these phenomena, amount of wear is seriously increased. On the other hand, it is found that scratches all around the worn surface were created by abrasive wear. There is no crater formed by crack propagation.

It is indicated that *in-situ* synthesized reinforcements in the TMCs prevent the crack propagation. As shown Fig. 8, the wear loss was inversely proportional to the reinforcement content. In generally, hardness of metal matrix composites is key factor to improve its wear resistance, especially in case of abrasion resistance. Actually owing to the TiB and TiC reinforcements, brinell hardness of TMCs were increased proportionally according to the B₄C content in Fig. 8. In the case of Ti-3.76wt% B₄C, the value of hardness is about 2 times harder than pure Ti. So it is possible to predict the improved wear resistance after friction test.

Fig. 8. Brinell hardness and wear loss of pure Ti and *in-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites.

The TMCs consisted of reinforcement, especially in 3.76wt%B₄C, effectively prevent the wear from scratching and cracking away matrix material during sliding, led to the slightly lower debris removal. In comparison with low content of reinforcement, 0.94 and 1.88wt%B₄C, it appeared quite different condition of wear. These particles which is mixed Ti matrix, reinforcements and oxidation is so hard formed by abrasion, adhesion and oxidation wear [12,13]. Wear debris included hard reinforcements between the sliding surface and counter-surface

brought the three-body abrasive wear and formed by transfer layer on the surface of TMCs [14].

Due to the transfer layer, it is prevented the direct contact called by two-body abrasion between the two surfaces and led to occur distribution of pressure concentration at asperity. As a result of this, wear resistance of TMCs is better with the reinforcements increased. In Fig. 7(b)-(g), it can be easily observed lots of particles on the surface. Actually it is transfer layer consisted of hardened particles caused by abrasion, adhesion and oxidation. According to expectation, the addition of the reinforcements was effective improving the wear resistance and friction characteristics of Ti.

Fig. 9. Inter-particle spacing of pure Ti and *in-situ* synthesized titanium matrix composites.

Moreover, to investigate the effect of B₄C size, we can contemplate the contact area of the Ti matrix against counterpart and fragmentation of reinforcements from the Ti matrix [15,16]. Dogan et. al. reported that, in low stress environment, wear resistance could be improved in the condition of smaller inter-particle (reinforcement) spacing owing to the effective protection of ductile matrix against the counterpart. However, in high stress environment, the higher inter-particle spacing by coarser reinforcement indicated that the wear resistance have the opposite tendency. In case of contact area of the Ti matrix against counterpart, TMCs by 150µm B₄C have lower inter-particle spacing between the matrix and reinforcement than 1500µm B₄C, as shown Fig 9. If the inter-particle spacing was large, the contact area of exposed ductile Ti was increased. Meanwhile, coarse

reinforcements by 1500 μm B₄C have a tendency to endure effectively than by 150 μm B₄C under applied load. Therefore, from the results of sliding wear test, it is believed that the fine reinforcements were easily fragmented from the Ti matrix than coarse reinforcements and fragmented debris accelerate the decrease of wear resistance. For the verification of the wear mechanism, the relationship between the applied load and reinforcement size/content will be investigated in the not too distant future.

4. Summary

Particulate-reinforced TMCs can be *in-situ* synthesized by investment casting, and the reinforcements were homogeneously distributed and there was no interfacial reaction between the matrix and reinforcements. The *in-situ* synthesized reinforcements due to the 150 μm B₄C were finer than those that resulted from 1500 μm B₄C. It is obvious that these results were caused because the fine B₄C particles promote the increase of the number of nucleation sites for the reinforcements. The *in-situ* (TiB+TiC) particulate reinforced TMCs owing to the fine B₄C exhibits a higher tensile property than by that of the coarser B₄C. The improvement of the tensile strength and ductility of the TMCs was caused by not only load transfer strengthening but also by matrix grain refinement and homogeneous distribution of the reinforcements. Moreover, the addition of the reinforcements was effective improving the wear resistance characteristics of Ti. Wear property of TMCs by fine and coarse reinforcements shows different results. It is believed that the different wear property between the fine and coarse reinforcement were caused by the distinction of the fragmentation of the reinforcements from the Ti matrix.

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